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A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“ECHO OF MY HEART”

You were a spark of life when you first appeared,
and I knew you when the world first began.
Alone, but never truly so-
I promised you when you were just a month old.

You and I have built our life together,
for better or worse, with happiness or conflict.
Burning with light, you chase your aspirations
at the age of seventeen, brave and bright.

You're intelligent, obstinate, and exquisitely free-
a reflection of myself, a mirror soul.
I proudly smile, but I secretly worry
about the world you'll have to face every turning year.

However, be aware of one unwavering truth:
my love endures no matter where life take you-
you and I will always be each other.